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The Effect of Non-Uniform Velocity Distribution on the Performance of Tethered Coaxial Turbines

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Abstract

Tethered, coaxial, counter-rotating turbines offer the advantage of operating in zero net-torque mode, thereby avoiding tether twisting and entanglements. Low-order models of coaxial turbines operating under *realistic conditions* are required to estimate turbine performance, levelized cost of energy and to design optimization strategies for farm layouts. When operating in ocean currents, coaxial turbines may experience non-uniform velocity conditions from two sources, namely velocity shear present in the ambient flow and shear associated with the turbulent wake from an upstream turbine in a farm configuration. The assertion of a turbine experiencing background shear due to the ambient flow is reinforced by acoustic doppler current profiler data presented in [1]. We have performed high-resolution LES simulations aimed at developing insights into the evolution of the wake from a tethered turbine operating over a range of shear conditions. Our simulations reveal that when the wake parameters are scaled by the local inlet velocity, the turbine wake exhibits a self-similar behavior, approximated by a Gaussian function. By varying the magnitude of the shear gradient, we are able to establish a relationship between the turbine wake growth rate and the shear magnitude. Our simulations of coaxial, counter-rotating turbines also show background shear enhances turbine wake vortices, leading to faster wake recovery and higher growth rate. The faster wake recovery will result in increased power performance of downstream turbines, informing optimization strategies for the turbine farm. Future work will focus on developing a low-order modification for the BEMT model introduced in [2] for coaxial turbine performance at different shear strengths.

Keywords: Marine Hydrokinetics; Sheared Flows; Ocean Current Turbines; Large Eddy Simulations

1. Introduction

Shear is an important phenomenon to consider when simulating the operating environment of an ocean current turbine. This effect becomes of greater importance when modeling coaxial counter-rotating ocean current turbines. Coaxial turbines operating in ocean currents may experience non-uniform velocity conditions from two sources, primarily velocity shear in the ambient flow and shear associated with the turbulent wake from an upstream turbine in a farm configuration. The current work presented is interested in the relationship between the wake generated by the windward rotor and the flow field encountered by the leeward rotor in the presence of background shear. In support of this motivation, velocity shear in the ocean has been observed in recent years as reported by the ‘Observations of velocity variations in the Gulf Stream off Cape Hatteras’ as seen in Figure 1 [1]. From [1], maximum values of background shear of 0.02 s^{-1} and $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ were observed in the depthwise and cross-shelf directions respectively. The collective impact of these flow phenomena on the overall flow must be considered to accurately simulate and study the performance of an OCT in realistic operating conditions.

Fig. 1. Observations of velocity variations in the Gulf Stream off Cape Hatteras [1]. Data obtained from time-averaged ADCP data from moored and vessel-mounted ADCP devices.

2. Methods

2.1 Model Setup

We utilized Siemens Simcenter Star-CCM+ ver.2022.1 in partnership with the University of North Carolina at Charlotte’s High Performance Computing Cluster to perform high fidelity Large Eddy Simulations. We implemented the Smagorinsky Sub-Grid Scale Model on a cartesian grid with dimensions shown and described in Figure 2 and Table 1 respectively. In order to study more singularly the effect of a non-uniform velocity distribution on the performance of the turbine, the simulations presented neglect all physical degrees of freedom of the turbine. Each turbine is instead modeled with the “Virtual Disk Model” native to Star-CCM+ ver.2022.1. The Blade Element Momentum method is employed; the coefficients of lift and drag are given as table inputs as functions of the local angle of attack and Reynolds number for a given radial position on the blade. The blades have a constant chord length of 0.02 meters and a constant sweep angle of zero degrees. The twist distribution is also an input given as a function of the radial location normalized by the total radius of the blade. The virtual disks are composed of three blades each with an inner radius of 0.015 meters, an outer radius of 0.1 meters, and a blade thickness of 0.0032 meters. The imposed rotation speed is a constant 40 radians/second, resulting in a Tip Speed Ratio of 4.

Fig. 2. Computational Domain.

Table 1. Simulations and turbine Parameters.

Parameter	Value
Rotor Diameter, D_t	0.2 m
Length	30 D_t
Height, Width	16 D_t
Distance Between Rotors	0.5 D_t
Total Cell Count	30 x 10 ⁶
Tip Speed Ratio	4
Ambient Velocity, u_∞	1 m/s
Shear Parameter, S	0 – 0.8

2.2 Boundary Conditions

The computational domain is initialized with a freestream velocity of 1 meter/second. For the inlet boundary, we apply a piecewise linear shear gradient to introduce a non-uniform velocity distribution. Figure 3 and Equation 1 detail the visualization and the definition of the inlet velocity distribution respectively. The velocity distribution is centered at the freestream velocity at a vertical position of $y = 0$ and varies linearly between the controllable position of $\pm H$. Beyond these positions, a uniform inflow velocity is imposed. Early simulations revealed disagreement between the top and bottom symmetry boundary conditions and a purely linear velocity gradient, thus, to mitigate these effects a piecewise linear-uniform velocity distribution was employed. For the outlet boundary we prescribe a pressure outlet boundary condition. To prevent flow recirculation, the backflow specification is set to boundary-normal. For the top, bottom, left, and right boundaries we apply a symmetry plane boundary condition. This serves to impose an infinite domain approximation in the lateral boundaries. The LES methodology and data were validated for a single-rotor with no shear case by comparing with the experiments of Mycek et al. [5], as detailed in [4].

Fig. 3. Visualization of Piecewise Linear Velocity Distribution

$$U_{in}(y) = \begin{cases} U_\infty(1 - S) & y < -H \\ U_\infty \left(1 + \frac{S}{H}y\right) & -H \leq y \leq +H \\ U_\infty(1 + S) & y > +H \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where,

U_{in} is the inlet velocity in meters/second,

U_∞ is the uniform velocity component in meters/second,

S is the non-dimensional shear parameter,

y is the cross-stream position in meters,
H is a variable position in the cross-stream direction in meters.

3. Results

3.1 Wake Definition

In studying the response of wake diameter and resulting growth rate to inlet velocity conditions, the definition for where the wake is taken to be is critical. Through a comparison of several methods for defining the wake-freestream boundary, the methods presented by Porté-Agel et al. (2020) [3] were deemed to be the most promising. The authors propose that for a self-similar wake, a gaussian distribution of the form presented in Equation 2 can adequately describe the velocity deficit profile of the wake. The wake radius is defined as the radial distance corresponding to one standard deviation of the normalized velocity deficit; since the wake is symmetric and self-similar, the velocity deficit profile is described by Equation 3. This produces a normalized definition for the wake without any dependence on radial position that is purely a function of the local centerline value for the normalized velocity deficit. Assuming a linear wake growth rate, the wake diameter can be represented as a function of streamwise position as seen in Equation 4. Differentiating with respect to streamwise position results in the expression for wake growth rate shown in Equation 5. The following shear-dependent wake diameters and wake growth rates results from the analysis of the equations presented.

$$\frac{\Delta \bar{u}}{\bar{u}_\infty} = C(x) \exp\left(-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\Delta \bar{u}}{\bar{u}_\infty} = C(x) \exp\left(\frac{-1}{2}\right) \approx 0.6 C(x) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\sigma}{d} = \alpha \frac{x}{d} + \epsilon \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial x} = \alpha \quad (5)$$

$$S = \gamma \frac{D_t}{u_\infty} \quad (6)$$

3.2 Wake Results

To study the effect of a non-uniform inlet velocity distribution on the turbine wake, we introduce a non-dimensional shear parameter, S, described in Equation 6. By varying the value of S, we can control the magnitude of the shear gradient introduced to the flow. We expect that, as the value of shear increases, the increased flow velocity in the freestream will interact more strongly with the reduced velocity of the wake, causing more rapid entrainment of the ambient flow into the wake region resulting in more rapid recovery of the wake. To investigate this, five LES simulations were performed in STAR-CCM+ imposing the inlet velocity distribution described in Equation 1. The value of the non-dimensional shear parameter, S, was then varied from 0 to 0.8 and a pair of virtual disks utilizing the Blade Element Momentum Method are simulated. For each case, the wake diameter was obtained from the radial location satisfying $r = \sigma$. The wake growth rate α is then obtained from eq. (5) for each case. Our baseline case ($S = 0$) had uniform (no-shear) inlet flow velocity, and is also included in the comparison in figure 4. Figure 4 (a) demonstrates this expected effect, plotting the wake growth rate calculated from Equations 2-5 for the five cases with values of non-dimensional shear ranging from 0 to 0.8 where a value of $S = 0$ corresponds to a uniform inlet velocity distribution. Figure 4 (b) compares the wake diameters resulting from Equations 2-5 for the baseline uniform velocity distribution ($S = 0$) case (red) and the strong shear ($S = 0.8$) case (blue). It can be seen that the wake grows more rapidly with increasing streamwise position in the strong shear condition than in the uniform condition. The rate of change of the wake diameter for the two cases is reflected in Figure 4 (a) as the leftmost and rightmost points corresponding to $S = 0$ and $S = 0.8$ respectively.

Fig. 4. (a) Wake Growth at Varying Shear Values; (b) Wake Diameters at Varying Shear Values.

4. Conclusions

We have performed high-fidelity LES simulations observing the effects of a non-uniform velocity distribution on the wake of a tethered coaxial turbine. Our simulations show background shear enhances turbine wake vortices, leading to a higher wake growth rate and faster wake recovery. The result of faster wake recovery in the presence of background shear informs optimization strategies for farm implementation of these devices. Future work is aimed at developing a low-order modification for the blade element momentum model introduced in [2] for coaxial turbine performance across a range of shear strengths.

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Appendix A. Paper Figures

Fig. 1. Observations of velocity variations in the Gulf Stream off Cape Hatteras [1].

Fig. 2. Computational Domain.

Fig. 3. Visualization of Piecewise Linear Velocity Distribution

Fig. 4. (a) Wake Growth at Varying Shear Values; (b) Wake Diameters at Varying Shear Values.

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